

FIGURES OF POLITENESS USED IN ENGLISH MOVIES**Akhmadjonov Avazbek**

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e-mail: xusanovaferede@gmail.com<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18440714>**ABSTRACT**

This study analyzed the politeness strategies in the film dialogues based on Louisa May Alcott's *Little Women*. 10 dialogues from the film were selected as research material and their pragmatic and linguistic features were studied using the method of qualitative analysis. The results of the analysis showed that expressions of gratitude, positive politeness and humility are the most used strategies in dialogues. Modal verbs and softening words help speakers convey their purpose in a polite and respectful manner. These results are consistent with the politeness principle theory of Brown and Levinson (1987). The research shows that film dialogues not only have artistic value, but also are a useful source for learning politeness in English.

Keywords: politeness strategies, cinematic discourse, *Little Women*, sociolinguistic features, interactional patterns, face-threatening acts, social harmony

Introduction

Language is a tool of social communication, and every communicative process reflects the speaker's purpose. This purpose is manifested through various linguistic expressions. During the speech process, the speaker employs politeness strategies to convey their intentions in a clearer, more meaningful, and more comprehensible manner. Politeness refines speech, enhances the effectiveness of communication, and helps sustain interaction. In this article, politeness expressions are analyzed based on dialogues taken from English-language films. The main goal of the research is to determine how polite expressions are used in the communication process in films. Politeness has been discussed in pragmatics and discourse analysis. Several researches has been discussed. One of the most influential frameworks is Brown and Levinson's Politeness Theory (1987), which explains how speakers manage face and social relationships through language. According to researchers, politeness strategies are used to minimize face-threatening acts and maintain social harmony.

Politeness strategies are important in everyday conversation as well as in works of art and films based on them. Especially in English-language films, social relations, cultural values and interpersonal relationships between characters are reflected through dialogues. Since movie dialogues are close to natural communication, they clearly show forms of address, polite requests, expressions of gratitude and indirect speech acts. This study aims to investigate the use of politeness strategies in English-language films. Dialogues from the film "*Little Women* (2019), based on Louisa May Alcott's *Little Women*, and were selected as research material. Family and social relations are widely covered in the film, which creates favorable conditions for the analysis of politeness strategies.

The main goal of this study is to identify the means of politeness used in film dialogues and to show their importance in the process of communication. The results of the research

serve to determine the ways in which politeness is manifested in film discourse and to expand the possibilities of using films as authentic material in learning English.

Leech (1983) also emphasizes the role of politeness in communication and proposes the Politeness Principle, which suggests that speakers use indirectness and politeness to achieve their goals. These theories serve as a theoretical basis for the analysis of politeness strategies, including dialogues in films.

Methodology

As a study, the dialogues of the film based on *Little Women* were used as a source of information. In the process of analysis, speakers' forms of address, polite requests, ability to convey a specific goal through politeness and politeness strategies were studied. In addition, elements such as indirect expressions, grammatical approach, modal verbs and mitigating words (e.g. "**please**", "**sorry**") were also considered. This method allows to study the natural communication in the film and to determine the level of use of politeness strategies. In this study, film dialogues based on *Louisa May Alcott's "Little Women"* were selected as research material. Since the film is based on a work of art, politeness strategies are naturally and clearly manifested in the speech process.

Qualitative analysis method was used in this research. Qualitative analysis is a research method that focuses on the qualitative study and interpretation of data, which focuses on meaning, context, and social processes rather than quantitative data (Creswell, 2014). This method allows the researcher to identify social and linguistic relations through in-depth analysis of speech, text, dialogue or other communicative materials.

The main features of qualitative analysis are as follows:

Contextual approach: The research object is studied in real life conditions.

Focus on meaning and perspective: Speakers' intentions, thoughts, and social role are analyzed.

Flexibility: Depending on the data collected, new categories or themes may be identified during the research process.

In the study of film dialogues, qualitative analysis is very useful for identifying politeness strategies, forms of address, polite requests, and indirect speech acts. At the same time, it is an effective tool for showing sociolinguistic features and interaction patterns of film discourse. 10 examples of politeness were selected from film dialogues and analyzed pragmatically and linguistically.

During the analysis, special attention was paid to the following means of politeness:

- **Application forms of speakers;**
- **Polite requests;**
- **Indirect expressions;**
- **Modal verbs (could, would, might);**
- **Softening units (please, excuse me, I'm afraid, etc.).**

The selected examples are placed in the form of a table (table 1.), and the politeness strategy used in each dialogue and its communicative function are explained. This method makes it possible to determine how polite strategies are used in the process of natural communication in film dialogues.

Results

The following section presents the outcomes of 10 selected dialogues from ‘*Little Women*’ (2019). Politeness strategies and their communicative tasks identified during the research are analyzed. The table below lists the politeness forms used in each dialogue and their explanation.

The selected examples made it possible to determine how the characters of the film used politeness tools aimed at maintaining respect, politeness and social distance in their interaction. In the process of analysis, the speakers' forms of address, polite requests, indirect expressions, modal verbs and mitigating units (for example, *please, thank you, I'm afraid*) were the main object of attention. The results show that expressions of gratitude, positive politeness, and humility are the most common strategies in film dialogues. By using modal verbs and softening words, speakers communicate their goals in a polite and respectful manner, which ensures that communication takes place in an efficient and socially appropriate manner. The table below lists selected dialogues and the politeness strategies used in them:

Table 1. Politeness strategies in selected dialogues from “Little Women”

N.	Dialogue excerpt	Politeness type	Linguistic device	Explanation
1.	I wish to see Mr. Dashwood	Formal request	“I wish to”	Polite and indirect way to make a request.
2.	Polite and indirect way to make a request.	Positive politeness	Compliment	Expresses admiration and builds social rapport.
3.	I feel sorry for you.	Empathy/ Sympathy	Empathic expression	Shows concern and understanding for the other person’s feelings.
4.	Thank you, Aunt March, for your employment and your many kindnesses.	Gratitude	Thank you	Expresses appreciation and respect.
5.	Latin is privilege. Please, you have to learn it. I can’t afford to lose this position.	Polite command/ softened directive	“Please” + modal verbs	Command softened by “please” and polite phrasing.
6.	Thank you for letting me go.	Gratitude	Thank you	Shows appreciation for permission granted.
7.	Thank you for the carriage, Mr. Laurence. I don’t know how to repay you.	Humility /gratitude	Modest expression	Shows respect and recognition of help.

8.	Your grateful friend and humble servant, James Laurence.	Humility	Humble expression	Indicates social distance and politeness in formal correspondence.
9.	My dear sister, you are too kind	Positive politeness	Terms of endearment	Expresses affection and appreciation.
10.	Expresses affection and appreciation.	Polite response/gratitude	Polite reply	Keeps conversation courteous and friendly.

As can be seen from the table, expressions of gratitude and positive politeness are most common in dialogues. Softening devices and indirect expressions allow speakers to convey their purpose in a polite and respectful manner. Through this, the dialogues in the film are expressed in a natural and socially acceptable form.

Discussion

The results of this study show that politeness plays an important role in English-language films, especially in films based on works of fiction. Politeness strategies are evident in such films. The strategies identified in the analysis address forms, polite requests, indirect expressions, modal verbs, and mitigating words help speakers communicate their goals in a clear, understandable, and culturally appropriate manner. As noted by Brown and Levinson (1987), politeness strategies are important in managing social relationships and maintaining face. The analysis conducted on the basis of this film also confirms their theories: in dialogues, the speakers communicate with each other carefully and politely, which increases the effectiveness of communication. Also, the results of the analysis show that the movie characters flexibly use politeness strategies in different contexts. For example, expressions of gratitude and humility strategies occur in both formal and informal situations, ensuring that communication is socially acceptable. Indirect expressions, softening words, and modal verbs (e.g., please, thank you, I'm afraid, could) allow speakers to convey their words in a polite and respectful tone, making dialogues natural and easy to read.

As can be seen from the results of the table, the most common strategies are expressions of gratitude (***gratitude expressions***), positive politeness (***positive politeness***), and humility (***humility***). These strategies help speakers achieve their goals and maintain personal and social relationships. At the same time, politeness tools used in the dialogues increase the artistic naturalness of the film and show the audience the natural rules of social communication. In general, the examples from the movie *Little Women* confirm the politeness principle theory of Brown and Levinson (1987): politeness strategies play an important role not only in maintaining interpersonal respect, but also in improving communication efficiency and stabilizing social relations. In this way, film dialogues not only have artistic value, but also serve as a convenient source for learning polite forms in English.

The results of this study revealed how politeness strategies are used in film dialogues. In the future, researchers may study the differences in politeness in film dialogues of other genres or languages. It would also be useful to explore the relationship between the politeness

strategies used in the film and their use in real-life conversations. This provides a deeper understanding of the cultural and communicative aspects of politeness and creates a practical resource for English language learners.

Conclusion

The results of this study show that politeness strategies in English-language films are important in improving the effectiveness of communication. Especially in films based on works of art, for example in the film *'Little Women' (2019)*, the forms of politeness and their communicative functions are clearly demonstrated. During the analysis, it was observed that the speakers tried to convey their goals in a clear and culturally acceptable way through forms of address, polite requests, indirect expressions, modal verbs and mitigating words. At the same time, politeness strategies allow you to manage social interactions and keep the conversation going smoothly. This research has demonstrated the possibility of analyzing politeness strategies in film discourse using film materials and revealed effective ways of using films as authentic material in English language learning. Future research could extend these results and focus more closely on the role of politeness strategies and their interactional patterns in films of different genres.

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